

SPECIFIC FUNCTIONS OF THE MODERN TOURIST MARKET

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Annotation:

This article examines the characteristics, functions, development factors, evaluation indicators and tasks of the modern tourist market. And at the same time, opinions and comments are given about the existence of a system of economic levers that ensures the optimal functioning of the tourism services market, the balance of demand and supply for tourist services, "money - services" exchange, money flows and flows of tourist services.

Аннотация:

В данной статье рассматриваются характеристики, функции, факторы развития, оценочные показатели и задачи современного туристского рынка. И в то же время приводятся мнения и комментарии о наличии системы экономических рычагов, обеспечивающих оптимальное функционирование рынка туристических услуг, баланс спроса и предложения на туристские услуги, обмен «деньги - услуги», денежные потоки. и потоки туристических услуг.

Key words: market, tourist service, sector, tourism, tourist product, tourist demand, demographic factor

Ключевые слова: рынок, туристская услуга, отрасль, туризм, туристский продукт, туристский спрос, демографический фактор.

The relationship between sellers and buyers and the prices they offer are important to satisfy the interests of both parties. Goods and services are of interest to buyers, who want to buy according to certain conditions. Sellers are interested in knowing the products they produce, consumer characteristics, and reasonable prices for buyers. Thus, the market performs an informational function, including a regulatory function.

In turn, the tourism market is a system of world economic relations, in which the process of converting tourist and excursion services into money and reverse conversion of money into tourist and excursion services takes place.

In tourism, the concept of "market" is used in three ways:

1. As a distinctive feature of the method of managing the economy, which differs from the distribution, administrative and command system; as a method of interaction between producers and consumers based on a decentralized, impersonal mechanism of price signals.
2. As an existing system of world economic relations, in which the process of converting tourist products into money and money into tourist products, that is, into the world tourist market, is carried out.
3. As an economic mechanism of interaction between sellers and buyers of tourist products, describing the economic relations that arise between them.

In other words, the tourism market is the sphere of manifestation of economic relations between producers and consumers of tourist products. If the economic interests of the tourist product producer and consumer coincide, then there will certainly be a deed of purchase and sale of the tourist product.

In the specialized literature on tourism, the tourism market is defined as a socio-economic phenomenon that combines supply and demand to ensure the process of buying and selling certain tourist goods and services at a certain time and place. The tourism market is an institution or mechanism that brings together buyers (demanders) and sellers (suppliers) of tourist services, unlike the usual commodity markets, the tourism market does not involve the transfer of goods from seller to buyer. On the contrary, customers themselves move to the destination to receive the ordered services. The tourism market is characterized by multi-level relationships, in which there are travel agencies, tour operators-generators, accommodation, transport and food service providers between the final consumer and the suppliers of tourism services. I.T.Balabanov and A.I.Balabanov define the tourist market as the sphere of realization of tourist products and the economic relations between buyers and sellers of tourist products.

The tourism market is characterized by the existence of subjects, that is, legal and physical persons who are producers and consumers of tourist products. The tourism market can be divided into three subjects: tourists themselves (consumers of tourist products), tour operators and travel agencies.

A tour operator (tour organizer) is a person who develops tourist routes and completes excursions, ensures their operation, organizes advertising, makes calculations in accordance with current standards and sets the prices of trips on these routes in the prescribed manner. a tourist organization that approves, sells tours to travel agencies to issue and sell tickets under their licenses.

A business entity that buys excursions on tourist destinations developed by a travel agency-tour operator, issues vouchers for them and sells these vouchers directly to tourists, or individual entrepreneur.

The counterparty is a legal entity or a natural person, acting in accordance with the legislation of the host country and international agreements, providing tourist services in the country (place) of arrival.

A tourist (consumer of tourist products) is a person who travels for any purpose other than seeking income and changing the place of permanent residence, with a stay of at least 24 hours outside the place of permanent residence.

The market performs many functions: information, intermediation, regulation, pricing, incentives, positive and negative differentiation. But the following can be distinguished as the main functions of the tourism market:

- 1) sale of added value and consumption value of tourist products;
- 2) organizing the process of delivering the tourist product to the consumer (tourist);
- 3) economic support for material incentives for work.

During the performance of the first function by the tourism market, value movement occurs, which is reflected by exchange: money ↔ tourist product.

The completion of this exchange means the completeness of the act of commodity-money relations, the sale of the value contained in the tourist product and the public recognition of

its consumption value. As a result, the normal process of social reproduction is ensured, funds for the development of the tourism industry appear and accumulate.

The application of the function of organizing the process of delivering the tourist product to the consumer is carried out by creating a network of travel agencies and tour operators.

The task of economic support of material incentives for labor is that distribution appears in its full form as a necessary stage of reproduction in the process of "money-tourist product" exchange in the tourism market. Employees of the tourism company, who receive monetary rewards for their work, create financial incentives to increase the quality and quantity of tourist products in accordance with consumer requirements, and to produce them.

The tourism market is a service market. It has its own characteristics that should be taken into account when organizing a tourist business.

First, tourist services:

a) intangible (when buying a tour, a tourist cannot try it, touch it or see it with his own eyes), so here is the reliability of the tourist product, the level and quality of services promised to tourists in advance guarantees of provision (ie, consistency of tourist product information and content) are important. Tourists require full information about the consumption characteristics of the species, compliance with the principle of the relationship between price and quality (consumers conditionally set the lower limit of the price for themselves, then the quality assumed to be low). Trust in the company is not only a matter of its reputation, but also of customers and market stability;

b) lost over time (revenue received from a service not provided in a certain period is lost forever) - here the efficiency of information and working with the customer's order, as well as responding to changes in demand and encouraging sales flexible, tiered pricing that encourages incentives is important;

c) the quality of individual services may change as part of a tour, therefore, prices should be differentiated according to the quality of services, replacement and service options.

Secondly, when selling a tourist product (be it a tour, excursion or pre-ordered hotel service), as a rule, there is a time difference between paying (buying) a tourist product and consuming it. A tourist buys a ticket for a trip in advance and continues the work of service organizations through a tour operator and a travel agency (that is, he pays the person who bought the ticket, not the service provider personally). Therefore, the reliability of the tourist product and its promotion channels, as well as the responsibility of the travel company that sells the product to the tourist, are important here.

Thirdly, the tourist market is characterized by significant seasonal changes in tourist demand. Moreover, these fluctuations are not the same for different types of tourism. Development of non-seasonal forms of recreation, provision of good rest for tourists in non-seasonal periods, skillful use of the material base for various types of tourism and seasonal regional difference - all this helps to reduce the seasonal losses of the tourism company.

Fourthly, the quality in tourism depends more on the performers, that is, on the service personnel (guides, guides, receptionists, servants, etc.) - employees of communication professions. Therefore, issues of tourism management, promotion of quality work, creation of a flexible tourist product are very important for a tourist enterprise.

Fifth, there is a territorial division of the consumer and the producer in the tourism market. Issues of advertising your product in other regions, relations with foreign partners are also important for the tourism business (forming a positive image of the tourist company, the

holiday region; establishing quick contacts with distant partners to facilitate the satisfaction of consumer demand).

Like all other markets, the tourism market operates according to the law of supply and demand.

The following factors affect tourist demand and, therefore, the tourism market:

Geographical and climatic conditions and natural-geological factors:

- good climate and favorable natural conditions;
- the presence of beautiful landscapes and natural attractions;
- existence of a developed hydrographic network and natural water bodies;
- cleanliness and preservation of natural objects, good state of ecology.

Demographic factors:

- Population growth. Increases tourism potential around the world;
- Increasing life expectancy and lowering the age-related pension limit.
- Ethnic tourist flows (traveling to the historical Motherland, immigrants, peoples with related languages and cultures, interest in mutual travel, etc.);
- More and more influx of youth tourism (adolescent, youth and student tourism);
- Middle-aged family travel trends (specialized family travel).

Political factors:

- Internal political stability of the country of residence;
- Internal political stability of the country receiving tourists;
- Peaceful, friendly, good neighborly relations between the states;
- Existence of interstate and intergovernmental agreements on cooperation in the field of economy, trade, scientific-technical and cultural relations, tourism and exchange.

Socio-economic factors:

- The standard of living of the main part of the population, that is, the economic existence of tourism;
- Social freedoms and rights that allow citizens to travel within and outside their country, to travel around the world;
- Activation of economic relations between countries on the basis of international division of labor, expansion of international trade and improvement of means of transport.

In conclusion, it should be said that as the tourist market continues to develop, new functions appear in it, the introduction of new terms, the emergence of new tourist services.

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